

Nationellt forensiskt centrum – NFC

Estimating volume of waste heaps

Reliable results on volume estimation by simulating uncertainty

1 Introduction

This document describes a study conducted by the Swedish National Forensic Centre (NFC), with the purpose of developing a new methodology for estimating volume of waste deposits in the form of heaps.

The study was performed as part of the European initiative PERIVALLON, which focuses on protecting the European territory from organised environmental crime through intelligent threat detection tools. More information about the PERIVALLON project is available at: <https://perivallon-he.eu/>

Intended readers of this document include PERIVALLON project members and other interested parties.

This document does not have a security protection classification, and thus may be freely distributed. For more information, please contact NFC at the below address:

Swedish Police Authority
National Forensic Centre – NFC
Sensor Technology
sensorteknik.nfc@polisen.se

2 References

- [r 1] Cyclone Register 360, Quick Start Guide
- [r 2] Zhang, Cha, and Tsuhan Chen. "Efficient feature extraction for 2D/3D objects in mesh representation". Proceedings 2001 International Conference on Image Processing (Cat. No. 01CH37205). Vol. 3. IEEE, 2001.

3 Tools

- [v 1] Cyclone Register 360 v2020.0.0 (Build r17339)
- [v 2] Autodesk 3dsMax 2021
- [v 3] CloudCompare v2.12
- [v 4] Agisoft Metashape Pro 1.6.2 build 10247 (64bit)
- [v 5] Leica RTC 360
- [v 6] Leica RTC 360
- [v 7] DJI Mavic 2 Pro

4 Case background

Data was collected from two separate locations (named in this document Site 1 and Site 2). The procedures followed were consistent for both sites, but as the sites are not identical there are naturally differences in the results. The specific Sites and waste Heaps are denoted in this document as S#H#.

Site 1 (S1) is a landfill / recycling plant consisting of four separate waste heaps. The heaps are composed of different waste types and have heterogenous material distribution, i.e. density:

- Heap composed of mixed waste, S1H1
- Heap composed of wood, S1H2
- Heap composed of stone and concrete, S1H3
- Heap with sieved waste, S1H4

Site 2 (S2) contains a larger waste heap which is very compressed, resulting in a high overall heap density:

- Heap composed of mixed waste, S2H1
- Separated heap composed of wood, S2H2

Figure 1 and Figure 2 below display overhead views of the heaps from both sites. The extent of the sieved heap S1H4 was difficult to define with regard to identifying the heap perimeter within the surrounding terrain. Due to this uncertainty, the relevant image is marked with a question mark.

Figure 1. Overhead view of Site 1. Left: the large mixed heap S1H1. Right (top down): heap with sieved waste S1H4, heap with stone/concrete S1H3, heap with wood S1H2.

Figure 2. Overhead view of Site 2. Left: the large mixed heap S2H1 and Right: the smaller excavated heap S2H2.

5 Analysis definition

5.1 Scope

The purpose of the study is to determine the volume of the waste heaps. The following scope was agreed to be produced within this study:

- 3D models of each waste heap
- An estimated volume for each waste heap
- An uncertainty analysis for each estimated volume

5.2 Delimitations

The density of each heap can be obtained through measurement of mass and volume. While volume can be estimated as described in this document, measuring mass is not straightforward. When waste is scooped up from a heap e.g. with a loader, it expands dramatically in volume. This scooped waste may be weighed, but the measured volume of the scooped waste will not be representative for its volume when integrated in the heap. The calculated density will thus be misleading. While it is possible to compensate for the scooped waste volume expansion, such an analysis was excluded from this study.

5.3 Methodology

To proceed with the waste heap investigation, it was necessary to develop a new methodology. Data collection would be performed with a Terrestrial 3D Laser Scanner (TLS) and from the air using an Unmanned Aerial System (UAS). Collected data would be used to generate 3D models, using the UAS images for photogrammetric reconstruction. The TLS data was intended to be used only to verify the photogrammetry results. The two models would be compared in order to obtain indicators of quality and uncertainty in the form of a deviation value dataset. This in turn together with the 3D photogrammetry model would be used to simulate an array of possible heap volumes.

6 Data collection

During the data collection of both Site 1 and Site 2, activities were overseen by NFC personnel together with the site owners. After a site walkthrough, data was collected using TLS and UAS.

6.1 Site 1

6.1.1 UAS

Image collection at Site 1 was performed by NFC personnel. The UAS used is documented as [v 7]. A total of 1913 images were collected in order to create a photogrammetric reconstruction of the site. Flight path altitudes of 30m and 50m were used. The app Pix4Dcapture was used as an aid in executing the flight path. Some images were taken manually. Data collection was performed primarily during daylight with an overcast sky, and with a light drizzle part of the time. Dusk was approaching towards the end of the data collection period.

6.1.2 TLS

Collection of 3D data with TLS was performed using two Leica RTC 360, [v 5] and [v 6]. It was not considered necessary to perform any contamination avoidance activities. Default settings were used. Scanning positions were equally spaced around the relevant waste heaps. Markers in the form of checkerboard laminated paper (size A4) were placed around the site for use as control points.

A total of 69 scans were performed to measure the entire area. Scans between the heaps were distributed to produce an overall satisfactory coverage. Parts of S1H1 were scanned with more spread out positions due to inaccessibility along one side of the heap. The activity was performed in parallel with the collection of UAS data, and therefore under the same light and weather conditions.

A site may be contaminated with moving objects or people during scanning. In order to filter out these contaminants from the final scan, the function “Double scan” is used to perform two scans over the same area from the same position. Where there is a difference between the scans, the measurement from the most remote position is retained and the proximal measurement is discarded. This is not necessary but saves time since such noise/contaminants otherwise need to be cleaned in the postprocessing step of the point clouds.

There was a recurring issue with Leica’s automatic registration during data collection, where the VIS function was not able to correlate a new scan’s relative position to that of a previous scan. It was possible to perform manual data registration, but the precision of this data could not be guaranteed during the data collection. As a result, it was not always possible to rely on the previews in Leica Cyclone Field 360.

Settings used in the data collection are shown in the table below.

Scan Nr.	Res	Colour	Comments
A001-A004, A006-A014, A016-A020 B001-B018, C001-C009	Medium	Yes	Scanning positions around waste heaps S1H2, S1H3 and S1H4. TLS setting “Double scan” was used to reduce the risk that moving objects would affect the results. All data utilised the VIS tracking function.
D001-D024	Medium	Yes	Scanning positions around waste heap S1H1. TLS setting “Double scan” was used to reduce the risk that moving objects would affect the results. All data utilised the VIS tracking function.

6.2 Site 2

6.2.1 UAS

Images were collected at Site 2 using UAS [v 7]. To create a photogrammetric reconstruction of the site, a total of 280 images were collected, with UAS flight altitude at 30m and 50m. Some images were taken manually, but most were planned in a flight path using the app Pix4Dcapture. The activity was performed in daylight with an overcast sky and light drizzle.

6.2.2 TLS

3D data for Site 2 was collected with TLS [v 5]. Default settings were used, and no actions to avoid contamination avoidance were deemed necessary. Scanning positions were equally spaced around the site, in order to include both the large waste heap and the small heap which was composed of material emergency personnel had excavated from the large heap during a fire. Markers in the form of checkerboard laminated paper (size A4) were placed around the site for use as control points.

As for Site 1, there was a recurring issue with Leica's automatic registration during data collection, where the VIS function was not able to correlate a new scan's relative position to a previous scan. It was possible to perform manual data registration, but the precision of this data could not be guaranteed. As a result, it was not always possible to rely on the previews in Leica Cyclone Field 360.

A total of 39 scans were performed on the large waste heap S2H1. Scanning was performed after the UAS had finished collecting images for photogrammetric reconstruction, although still during daylight with overcast, drizzly conditions.

Settings used in the data collection are shown in the table below. The collection operation was controlled via iPad. A safety copy of the raw data was made in conjunction with data retrieval at NFC premises the day after it was collected.

Scan Nr.	Res	Colour	Comments
001-039	Medium	No	Scanning positions around waste heap S2H1. TLS setting "Double scan" was not necessary as no other people or vehicles were at the site. All collection utilized the VIS tracking function.

7 Data processing

7.1 TLS – Site 1 S1H1

Processing and registration of point clouds were performed using Cyclone Register 360 [v 1]. Post-processing was done using instructions in the Leica manual [r 1]. For heap S1H1, 24 scans were used and required manual adjustment before the software could register links between scan positions with the required precision. Figure 3 below shows an overhead view of the registered scan positions.

Figure 3. Overhead view of all registered scanning positions for S1H1.

7.2 TLS – Site 1 S1H2, S1H3 and S1H4

Processing and registration of point clouds was performed using Cyclone Register 360 [v 1]. Post-processing was done using instructions in the Leica manual [r 1]. Heaps S1H2, S1H3 and S1H4 were registered together and required 45 scans. Figure 4 below shows an overhead view of the registered scan positions.

Figure 4. Overhead view of all registered scanning positions for heaps S1H2, S1H3 and S1H4.

7.3 TLS – Site 2 S2H1 and S2H2

Processing and registration of point clouds was performed using Cyclone Register 360 [v 1]. Post-processing was done using instructions in the Leica manual [r 1]. Scans 001-039 were difficult to use due to disturbance from open fields and noisy data in areas covered by vegetation. Some scan parts could therefore not be registered with sufficient precision. A decision was taken to only utilize the parts with good registration, which included the first 25 scan positions. Figure 5 below shows an overhead view of the registered scan positions.

Figure 5. Overhead view of all registered scanning positions. Positions with a cross did not result in an acceptable precision and were therefore excluded from the 3D model.

7.4 UAS – creation of photogrammetric models

All photogrammetric 3D models were created by NFC personnel. The work was performed with Metashape [v 4]. The below steps were followed in the creation of the 3D models:

1. UAS images imported into MetaShape
2. Generation of a sparse point cloud and estimation of cameras with the function “Align Photos”
3. Registration of the model in the laser scanner’s coordinate system by identifying corresponding control points in each model, which are then linked (MetaShape and Cloud Compare)
4. Generation of a dense point cloud and filtering to remove points with a low level of confidence, without affecting the object’s geometry (Metashape)
5. Generation of a surface model from the filtered point cloud with texture (Metashape)
6. For each heap in the common mesh for the site, the heaps were clipped out to individual mesh objects.
7. All individual mesh objects were adjusted to reduce the number of polygons, in order to reduce complexity and hence processing time for the ensuing analyses. The complexity was set so that the heap’s overall geometry was not affected. (Metashape)

The results of these steps were four object models from Site 1 and two object models from Site 2. Step 2 above could not be performed for Site 2 with the laminated A4 markers, as they had been moved between the collection of photogrammetry images and the collection of TLS data. Specific features which could be identified precisely in the terrain in both the TLS model and photogrammetry images were used as alternate control points. Step 3 was thus performed for Site 2 using this method.

8 Data analysis

Heap volume is calculated from the photogrammetric model, as the laser scanned model does not have full coverage and therefore lacks information needed to create a correct overall model. Volume calculation from a model requires that it be closed. This is not the case for this study's data collection, as information regarding the bottom of each heap is not available. In order to complete the analysis, the 3D models are closed manually.

The calculated volume results can then be assessed by running an uncertainty analysis, based on the uncertainty in the model itself. The exact level of uncertainty/precision/correctness of the photogrammetric model is unknown, but it can be estimated through validation against the laser scanned model. The uncertainty of the laser scanned points is considered relatively negligible and is assumed to be "correct."

Each heap model was post-processed and analysed by NFC personnel according to the following sections.

8.1 Create ground plane and close openings in clipped mesh

The analyses in this study assume that all waste heaps have a flat base, e.g. a concrete slab. When the ground plane and sub-surface geometry is unknown, it is not possible to generate a reliable volume estimation.

For heap S2H2, the ground plane was closed in Metashape [v 4] using the function "Close holes." As the heap was located on flat ground, when this function was run it created the flat surface necessary to close the model.

For the other heaps, 3D models in the form of obj files were imported into 3dsMax [v 2] in order to create a ground plane and remove edges outside this plane along the sides of the models. Vertical surfaces were created for these side edges resulting in a completely closed model.

A volume calculation for S1H4 was not performed, as it was determined that a ground plane with reliable geometry could not be determined.

8.2 Deviation analysis

The closed heap model and corresponding part of the laser scan point cloud data were imported into CloudCompare [v 3]. Both models were checked visually for correct registration i.e. correlation with each other. Laser point data outside of the actual heap was excluded. The function "Cloud-to-mesh" was executed for the deviation analysis.

The deviation calculation was set as a C2M-signed-distance where the distance from the laser points to the nearest polygon was measured in the direction of the normal vector. This resulted in a deviation vector with the same length as the number of points in the point cloud (one

deviation per point). The deviation vector was saved in order to use it in a volume uncertainty propagation.

Figure 6. Heap deviation values. Heap ID below each image.

8.3 Volume uncertainty propagation

The volume of the closed mesh is the total volume of all tetrahedrons created from the mesh's triangles and origin, according to [r 2].

The deviation values describe how the mesh geometry deviates from that of the laser point cloud. As the mesh geometry is determined by the vertex positions, shifting the vertex points changes the mesh geometry, see Figure 7. The shift for a vertex point's coordinates $\{x,y,z\}$ is determined by randomly generating three values $(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ from the deviation array and adding them to the start coordinates – known as bootstrapping. The vertex points' new coordinates are shifted to $\{x+\Delta x, y+\Delta y, z+\Delta z\}$.

Figure 7. Illustration of vertex point shift. Left: before shift. Right: after shift, with old vertex positions greyed out.

A new possible volume is calculated from the changed mesh geometry after the vertex point shift. This procedure is repeated 10 000 times, resulting in as many heap form variants and possible heap volumes.

Uncertainty propagation has been executed using a script which was created as part of this study. The closed mesh and associated deviation values were used as input for the simulation, which resulted in a distribution graph of possible volumes. This procedure was followed for all heaps.

9 Results

The results for Site 1 and Site 2 are reported separately in the following sections. The results consist of calculated volume with accompanying uncertainty interval.

9.1.1 Site 1 volume

The table below reports the calculated volume for each heap. The volume of heap H4 could not be determined due to the inability to precisely establish the heap boundary. The figures show the simulation results, with 10 000 calculations per heap.

Heap name	Volume [m ³]	
	median	min – max (3σ)
S1H1	37 125	36 987 – 37 264
S1H2	5 569	5 550 – 5 587
S1H3	3 865	3 844 – 3 887
S1H4	-	-

S1H1:
median volume 37 125 m³

S1H2:
median volume 5 569 m³

S1H3:
median volume 3 865 m³

9.2 Site 2 volume

The table below reports the calculated volume for each heap. The figures show the simulation results, with 10 000 calculations per heap.

Heap name	Volume [m ³]	
	median	min – max (3σ)
S2H1	41 681	41 565 – 41 797
S2H2	2 629	2 530 – 2 729

S2H1: median volume 41 681 m³

S2H2: median volume 2 629 m³

10 Future work

Measuring density introduces new problems, i.e. when scooping up waste with a loader to weigh on a scale, the compactness changes and the volume expands. Therefore, NFC proposes to measure volume before and after representative amounts have been removed. This is a future work which falls within the ongoing EU project PERIVALLON, together with refinement of the method for volume estimation with uncertainty analysis.

PERIVALLON

nfc.polisen.se

Nationellt forensiskt centrum – NFC
581 94 Linköping, Telefon 010-562 80 20
e-post registrator.nfc@polisen.se

Swedish National Forensic Centre – NFC
SE-581 94 Linköping, Tel +46 10 562 80 20
e-mail registrator.nfc@polisen.se

